

A Cobb-Douglas Analysis of Mining & Quarrying Sector in India

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Abstract : *This study investigates the production relationship within the Indian mining and quarrying sector using the Cobb-Douglas production function. The study aims to achieve three key objectives, including describing the production relationship, analysing returns to scale, and determining factor shares. The Indian mineral industry plays a vital role in the economy, with a significant increase in the mineral production index and total value in 2021-2022. The sector consists of metallic and non-metallic minerals, driving industrial growth. The mining and quarrying sector contributed about 2.40% of Gross Value Added, with 93% of mines concentrated in eleven key states in India. The paper aims to estimate the function's parameters and analyse returns to scale and factor shares within the industry. By utilizing industry-level data from 1981 to 2023, the study explores the impact of labour, capital, and energy inputs on value added. The study utilizes linear regression and robust models to analyse the data, addressing issues such as normality, autocorrelation, and heteroskedasticity. The findings reveal that, a 1-unit consumption in energy leads to a -.402 percent point decrease in value added, highlighting the importance of reducing energy consumption for efficiency in the mining and quarrying industry. This also indicates energy used inefficiently, possibly more energy consumed without proportional increase in the value added or there is more wastage of energy or industries using outdated technology. The aggregate value of the coefficient is positive, suggesting increasing returns to scale. Most explanatory variables are significant at the 99% level, indicating their substantial contribution to defining the production model. The goodness of fit measure R^2 indicates that approximately 96% of the*

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variations in the data can be explained using the specified model. Moreover, it was observed that a higher capital-to-labour ratio leads to a decrease in the rate of substituting capital for labour, indicating diminishing marginal returns to capital or increasing costs of substitution. This research underscores the importance of understanding production dynamics and resource allocation in the mining and quarrying sector to inform policy and investment decisions for sustainable economic growth in India.

Keywords : Mining & Quarrying Production, Cobb-Douglas Production Function, Marginal Rate of Technical Substitution.

Introduction to India's Mineral Industry

The mining and quarrying sector plays a crucial role in the Indian economy, providing raw materials for various industries. Lack of access to natural resources would jeopardize the progress of any community. Mineral development has the power to build new towns and enrich existing ones. Significant production capacity in other industries, such the construction and mining sectors, will be made possible by the development of mines and the best possible use of mineral deposits. According to a World Bank analysis from 2002 on mining operations worldwide, for every US dollar spent on a mine by a business, 2.80 US dollars are generated elsewhere in the economy.

India's mineral industry plays a vital role in the country's economy, with a rich history dating back to ancient civilizations like the Harappan. The sector encompasses a diverse range of metallic and non-metallic minerals, driving industrial growth and development. The trend in mineral production can be understood as India boasts a significant mineral production sector, contributing to various industries. The mineral production index for 2021-22 displayed positive growth, reaching 113.3, showcasing a 12.17% increase from the previous year. The total value of mineral production surged to Rs. 211857 crores, reflecting a substantial 31.96% rise over the previous year. Metallic minerals constituted a substantial portion, representing 57.65% of the total value, while non-metallic minerals accounted for the remaining 42.35%. Wholesale Price Index for minerals exhibited positive growth in 2021-22. The mining and quarrying sector contributed about 2.40% of Gross Value Added in the same year. On the other hand, the Indian mining industry is characterized by numerous small operational mines spread across different states. Notably, in 2021-22, 93% of mines were concentrated in eleven key states, showcasing regional disparities. The

distribution of mining leases varies significantly by area, providing insights into the geographic spread of mining activities across India. Several states stood out in terms of mineral production, with Odisha leading the pack. While some states reported increases in mineral production, others witnessed declines, highlighting the dynamic nature of the industry. India's mineral reserves and resources are crucial for sustaining its mining industry and overall economic growth, guiding future planning and development initiatives.

India's mineral business has a long history that dates back to the country's ancient civilizations and contributes significantly to the economy of the nation. The mineral production index increased by 12.17% in 2021-2022 to reach 113.3, while the total value increased by 31.96% to Rs. 211857 crores. Of Gross Value Added, the mining and quarrying industry generated around 2.40%. Small active mines dispersed over many states, with Odisha leading the way, are the industry's defining feature. India's natural resources and reserves are essential to the country's industry's survival and economic expansion.

Literature Review

Nurunnajib, A.F., Wulan, E.R., Awalluddin, A.S., Supian, S., & Subiyanto, S. (2018) discuss one of the production functions that show the relationship between the level of output and the level of input combinations which is called Cobb-Douglas production function. The estimation method used is the least square estimation with the settlement using Newton Raphson iteration. The Cobb-Douglas production function is applied to five selected manufacturing industries in West Sumatra. From the research results, the return to scale (RTS) of the rubber and plastic goods industry is 0.8424 and the return to scale of the food and beverage industry is 0.8496 in which the two industries produce $RTS < 1$. Whereas return to scale of the publishing and printing industry is 1.0460, the return to scale of the textile industry is 1.0018, and the return to scale of the non-metallic mining industry is 1.3384. Each of these three industries produces $RTS > 1$.

A series of studies have utilized the Cobb-Douglas production function to analyze industrial performance in India. Ghoshal (2017) applied this model to the agricultural sector, finding that road infrastructure and the share of agricultural NSDP to state NSDP were significant factors in production inefficiencies.

R. Edokpia, M. Oladeinde (2017) applies the Cobb-Douglas production function to evaluate a manufacturing firm's productivity in Nigeria, finding it mostly technically efficient but with periods of operating below the production frontier, indicating a potential future decrease in productivity.

Khatun, Sadia Afroze (2017) explore the relationship between real GDP and labour/capital in selected Asian countries, emphasizing the importance of investing in the labour force and capital for sustained growth, with significant contributions of both factors to productivity and increasing returns to scale.

Peter, Pesala (2017) discusses the influence of workers, fixed capital, and factories on output growth in different industries during pre and post-globalization periods, highlighting specific industries where each factor had a significant impact on output growth, and suggesting government incentives related to fixed capital for industries lacking sufficient levels of fixed capital.

Bhatt (2014) focused on small and medium enterprises, determining that labour was a more influential factor in output than fixed capital.

Manonmani (2013) extended this analysis to the manufacturing sector, identifying increasing returns to scale in certain sectors and a higher percentage share of wages compared to capital. These studies collectively highlight the utility of the Cobb-Douglas production function in understanding the complexities of industrial performance in India.

M Manonmani (2013) discusses the use of a Cobb Douglas production function to measure the contributions of labour, capital, and technology in the Indian economy, emphasizing the importance of technological change in economic growth and the role of the production function as a tool for macroeconomic analysis.

Peter, P., & Vadlamudi, R. (2012) analyse the data by calculating Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for different years and different variables like workers, fixed capital and output collected for 62 manufacturing industries from the Annual Survey of Industries (ASI) in Andhra Pradesh. In general, Cobb-Douglas production function has been used in two variables framework and value added has been considered as output and labour and capital as inputs. The Cobb-Douglas production function analysis through panel data analysis was done. The study followed the 1998-99, National Industrial Classification (NIC). The main findings of the study are, firstly, not all industries influenced the output growth. Secondly, most of the industries (20 industries) did not provide employment opportunities. Thirdly, a few (18) manufacturing industries' fixed capital CAGR has negatively declined. Fourthly, a few (12) manufacturing industries' output CAGR has negatively declined. And, finally only manufacture of machinery and equipment industry's workers per factory employed average declined, and rest of the industries' average number of workers per factory employed increased.

Agarwal, A.L. (1986). discusses the decline in industrial production growth rate in Indian industries after the mid-sixties, emphasizing the importance of studying the selected periods and industries at different classification levels.

Somayajulu, V. V. N. and Jacob P. George (1983) discuss theoretical and empirical problems related to estimating production functions in Indian industries, analysing factors such as output growth, returns to scale, productivity indices, technical progress, and elasticity of factor substitution using data from 1946 to 1975.

Bhasin, Seth (1980) estimates production functions for Indian manufacturing industries, finding that the C.E.S. production function is the most suitable specification due to lower elasticity of substitution, with inter-industry differences in returns to scale and income distribution.

G. Narasimham, M. Z. Fabrycy (1974) aim to measure the relative efficiencies of manufacturing industries in India using a production analysis based on the Cobb-Douglas production function, considering variables like investment, education, and experience. It finds significant differences in the efficiency of input use among different industries.

Gupta (1972) analyses the production function of the Indian cement industry from 1946 to 1965, suggests guidelines for industry expansion based on factors like labour, capital, and raw material inputs, and emphasizes the importance of region-specific strategies for improving efficiency.

The Cobb Douglas production function is utilized to analyse industrial performance in various countries and sectors. Studies highlight the relationship between real GDP, labour, and capital, demonstrating their significant contributions to productivity and returns to scale. Findings from panel data analysis show varied impacts on output growth and employment opportunities across different manufacturing industries. The function's application extends to evaluating productivity in agriculture, manufacturing, and small enterprises in countries like India, Nigeria, and Asian nations. Different industries exhibit varying levels of returns to scale, emphasizing the importance of understanding input combinations for optimal output levels.

Objectives of the Study

1. To describe the Production Relationship: is to estimate the model to understand how value added in mining and quarrying responds to changes in key inputs like labour and capital, energy.

2. To analyse Returns to Scale: The estimated coefficients will be used to determine the returns to scale in the industry. This will reveal if increasing inputs lead to proportionally greater, equal, or less than proportional increases in value added.
3. To determine Factor Shares: By analysing the estimated coefficients, we can identify the relative contribution of labour and capital to the value added generated in the sector.

Data Source and Methodology

The production function can be explained as a technical association between the physical quantity of output and physical quantities of inputs, such as labour, capital, energy, Material and service of the firm, industry sector or country.

The most popular form of the production function is the Cobb-Douglas function which can be expressed as

$$Y(L, K) = AL^\alpha K^\beta$$

Where Y is the output or value added, A is a scalar that can be thought of as the general level of technology used in production, L is a measure of the flow of labour input such as number of workers or total man days, K is a measure of the flow of capital input, which is a measure of value of all machinery, equipment and buildings. α and β are coefficients or parameters that measure the contributions of L and K, respectively, to the production of the output. The equation of the cobb- Douglas production function shows how a specific plant, firm, industry or economy's output level Y is determined from its factor inputs, such as labour (L) and capital (K).

Often estimated parameters help in knowing the stage or scale of production. If the $\alpha + \beta = 1$. It is called constant returns to scale means a 1% increase in inputs leads to the same percentage point increase in output. If $\alpha + \beta < 1$, it is considered return to scale a is decreasing means a 1% increase in inputs lead to less than 1% increase in output. $\alpha + \beta > 1$, returns to scale are increasing indicating that a 1 percent increase in input leads to more than 1percent increase in output.

If the Cobb-Douglas production function is a nonlinear function between the factor inputs L and K and the output Y, to know the parameters, we need to estimate the function using the data. More specifically, to know the value of the parameters α and β , and A, we require to transform the nonlinear cobb-Douglas

to a linear function so the OLS estimator can be employed. This can be done easily by converting all variables into logarithmic values, it is made a log-log model. This property of the model is another reason for the popularity of the Cobb-Douglas function in empirical research. To convert it into log-log model, we take the natural log of both sides of

$Y(L, K) = AL^\alpha K^\beta$ which will give :

$$\ln Y = \ln(A) + \alpha \ln(L) + \beta \ln(K)$$

Once the equation is made a linear log-log model, the OLS estimator can be applied for estimating parameters. The mining & quarrying production data of India for the year 1981 to 2023, from the KLEMS database. We use gross value added as a measure of output in rupees lakh, while labour data is proxied by the number of persons engaged in the industry. For capital input, we use the gross value of plant and machinery in Rupees lakh. All these variables are converted into logarithms.

Results and Interpretation

Table-1 : Descriptive Statistics on Mining & Quarrying

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
In Value Added	1.657	.044	1.559	1.713
In Energy	1.422	.045	1.31	1.498
In Capital	1.48	.104	1.245	1.622
In Service	1.452	.097	1.248	1.597
In Labour	1.21	.025	1.152	1.23

Table-2 : Matrix of Correlations on Mining & Quarrying

Variables	In VA	In K	In S	In L	In E
In Value Added	1.000				
In Capital	0.955	1.000			
In Service	0.928	0.992	1.000		
In Labour	0.238	0.078	0.053	1.000	
In Energy	0.815	0.922	0.951	0.053	1.000

The table-2 shows evidence of a strong positive correlation (0.955) between value added and capital suggesting increased capital investment (machinery, equipment) leading to a significant rise in value added. This implies that investing

in capital is likely to enhance productivity, resulting in higher economic output for the sector. Similarly, value-added shows a high Positive correlation (0.928) with services indicating a positive relationship. Hence improving services (maintenance, logistics, support) contributes to overall value added in mining and quarrying. Moreover, efficient and reliable services are likely to ensure smoother operations, thereby increasing output. A weak correlation of (0.238) between Value added and Labour suggests that labour's impact on value added is less prominent. Labour efficiency and skill development might play a role, but it's not the primary driver of value-added. This could indicate increasing automation or a shift towards capital-intensive processes in the industry whereas a strong positive correlation of (0.815) between value-added and energy implies that increased energy use is often associated with higher output levels. However, it's crucial to consider efficient energy use and sustainable practices to optimize economic outcomes.

Table-3 : Linear Regression on Mining & Quarrying

In Value Added	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
In Energy	-.402	.121	-3.31	.002	-.648	-.156	***
In Capital	.57	.131	4.34	0	.304	.836	***
In Service	-.016	.177	-0.09	.928	-.374	.342	
In Labour	.278	.057	4.89	0	.163	.393	***
Constant	1.073	.107	9.99	0	.856	1.291	***
Mean dependent var		1.657	SD dependent var			0.044	
R-squared		0.964	Number of obs			43	
F-test		257.119	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		-280.965	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			-272.159	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Table-4 : Linear Regression (Robust) on Mining & Quarrying

InValue Added	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InEnergy	-.402	.098	-4.12	0	-.6	-.205	***
InCapital	.57	.128	4.44	0	.31	.83	***
InService	-.016	.159	-0.10	.921	-.338	.306	
InLabour	.278	.063	4.43	0	.151	.405	***
Constant	1.073	.09	11.92	0	.891	1.256	***
Mean dependent var		1.657	SD dependent var			0.044	
R-squared		0.964	Number of obs			43	
F-test		362.751	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		-280.965	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			-272.159	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Table-5 : Skewness/Kurtosis Tests for Normality

Variable	Pr (Skewness)	Pr (Kurtosis)	adj chi2(2)	Prob>chi2
Residuals	0.4205	0.0226	5.57	0.0616

The probability values of skewness and kurtosis 0.4205 and 0.022 indicate normality of the data, as the significance level is greater than the conventional level of 0.05 percent.

Table-6 : Breusch-Godfrey LM Test for Autocorrelation

lags(p)	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
1	14.499	1	0.0001

H0: no serial correlation

Table-7 : Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg Test for Heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance			
Variables: Fitted values of ln VA			
chi2(1)	=	2.14	Prob > chi2 = 0.01436

The Breusch-Pagan test for heteroskedasticity shows that the probability value of the chi-square statistic is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis of constant variance can be rejected at a 5% level of significance. It implies the presence of heteroscedasticity in the residuals. So, to correct heteroscedasticity the following Robust model has been constructed in table number four.

The above table number four presents the results of OLS (Robust) after correcting for heteroskedasticity in the model. Thus, the problem of heteroscedasticity is not present anymore. This gives robust standard errors, which are different from standard errors in table-3. Here robust standard error for the variable lnE is 0.098, which is different from 0.121 given in table-3.

The results provide an estimate of the coefficients or parameters of labour, capital, energy, material & service. It can be noticed that estimates, while statistically significant, also make sense. The 0.278 is the estimate for labour, -.402 is the estimate for Energy, -.016 is the estimate for services and 0.57 is for capital. The -.402 estimate for β_1 indicates that a 1 percent growth in the energy causes a -.402 percent point decrease in the value added, this suggests that finding

ways to reduce energy consumption could be an important strategy for improving efficiency in the mining and quarrying industry. However, the aggregate value is more than one, $\alpha + \beta > -0.402 + 0.57 - 0.016 + 0.27 = .43$ which implies sum coefficient (0.43) is positive, which satisfactorily indicates increasing returns to scale. If all other inputs are held constant, a 1% increase in each of these four factors (energy, capital, service, and labour) would likely lead to a 0.43% increase in value added.

For instance, a 10 percent increase in all inputs would lead more than a 10 percent increase in the physical output. Except for Service all the explanatory variables are significant at 99% level. This shows that most of the variables are contributing to define the production model significant. Moreover, the measure of the goodness of fit R^2 with a value of 0.96 reveals that approximately 96% of variations in the data can be explained using this specified model.

The Marginal rate of substitution will measure the responses of the production scale with a change in the quantity of inputs (Cobb and Douglas 1928). For example, the marginal rate of substitution related to energy with one of the other input factors such as capital can be obtained from the following relation:

$$MRTS_{E/K} = \frac{-0.40}{0.57} \times \frac{K}{E}$$

The above relationship indicates more capital relative to labour, the MRTS decreases, and vice versa, implying that as a firm increases the ratio of capital to labour (more capital-intensive production), the rate at which it can substitute capital for labour diminishes. This might suggest diminishing marginal returns to capital or increasing costs of substitution as one input becomes relatively more abundant compared to the other.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis, it is evident that the Indian mining and quarrying sector contributes significantly to the economy, amounting to about 2.40% of Gross Value Added and being concentrated in eleven key states in India. The study utilized the Cobb Douglas production function for analysis, using data spanning from 1981 to 2023 for estimation and analysis. In the process, it was found that a higher capital-to-labour ratio leads to diminishing marginal returns to capital or increased costs of substitution, and the study employed linear regression and robust models to address issues related to data interpretation. The literature

review revealed that the Cobb Douglas function has been widely utilized in various sectors like agriculture and manufacturing, with a focus on important factors such as labour, capital, and technology for efficiency. From an economic standpoint, the study underscored the significance of understanding production dynamics for informed policy decisions, with the strong model explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.96$) further emphasizing its applicability in guiding economic policies and investments. The findings reveal that, a 1-unit consumption in energy leads to a -0.402 percent point decrease in value added, highlighting the importance of reducing energy consumption for efficiency in the mining and quarrying industry. Also indicates energy used inefficiently, possibly more energy consumed without proportional increase in the value added or there is more wastage of energy or industries using outdated technology. Overall, the analysis shed light on the importance of input ratios and production dynamics, highlighting the crucial role of understanding the production relationship in shaping economic policies and investments.

Policy Implications

The study on the production relationship within the Indian mining and quarrying sector utilizing the Cobb Douglas production function unveils various implications. Firstly, the identified increasing returns to scale point towards targeted policy interventions that could enhance production efficiency and increase output within the mining sector. Secondly, understanding the significant factors affecting production, such as capital, energy, material, and services, can streamline resource allocation strategies to optimize productivity. Thirdly, as the mining and quarrying sector significantly contributes to India's Gross Value Added, the findings can guide strategies for economic growth and development. Furthermore, insights from the study can pinpoint areas for improvement to boost the competitiveness of the Indian mining and quarrying industry at both national and global levels. Lastly, the research paves the way for future investigations in industrial performance using the Cobb Douglas production function, laying a foundation for deeper exploration of production relationships in various sectors and regions. In essence, these findings offer practical implications for policymakers, industry stakeholders, researchers, and economists seeking to refine production processes, allocate resources effectively, and stimulate economic growth in the Indian mining and quarrying sector.

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